

The Id, Ego, and Super-Ego – A Comparative Study of *Pride and Prejudice* and *Wuthering Heights*

Honghui Yang*

School of Foreign Studies, University of Science and Technology Beijing, Beijing, China

Article Information

Suggested Citation:

Yang, H. (2023). The Id, Ego, and Super-Ego – A Comparative Study of *Pride and Prejudice* and *Wuthering Heights*. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(2), 79-83.

DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(2\).08](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(2).08)

* Corresponding author:

Honghui Yang

e-mail: 1027848716@qq.com

Abstract:

Pride and Prejudice and *Wuthering Heights* are regarded as seminal works from the Victorian era, having received extensive scholarly interest. Written by Jane Austen, who is widely recognized as one of the greatest English writers, *Pride and Prejudice* has remained popular among readers since its first publication. Scholars have analyzed the novel from multiple angles, including feminist, Marxist, and psychological perspectives, further cementing its status as a significant work of literature. On the contrary, Emily Bronte's *Wuthering Heights* did not enjoy the same level of recognition during its initial release and only gained widespread acclaim until the 20th century. As time passed, the novel's reputation has grown to be on par with that of *Pride and Prejudice*. However, the comparison between

the two novels is neglected by scholars. This essay aims to fill that gap by examining the two heroines, Elizabeth and Catherine, using Sigmund Freud's id, ego, and superego framework.

Keywords: *Id, Ego, Superego, Pride and Prejudice, Wuthering Heights.*

Introduction

Both *Pride and Prejudice* and *Wuthering Heights* are seminal works of the Victorian period, which have garnered significant critical acclaim and scholarly attention. *Pride and Prejudice* is written by Jane Austen, who is widely regarded as one of the greatest writers in English literature. Since its publication, the feminism in the novel is astutely noticed by scholars, for example, Sultana reveals "women were always considered inferior to men, and the perception of the categorical inferiority of women by men is as old as recorded time" (Sultana, 2012). Awan and Ambreen turn concern to Marxism. They demonstrate Marxism's impact: "Society and even people's attitude are shaped by wealth, class and marriage, the chief concerns of Marxism" (Awan & Ambreen, 2018). The psychological analysis is

also an inevitable approach to demonstrating characters in the novel: "As they develop their romantic bond, the novel's lovers, Elizabeth Bennet and Fitzwilliam Darcy, move from one psychological position to another" (Almond, 1989). On the contrary, *Wuthering Heights* by Emily Bronte did not receive widespread recognition from the academic community upon its initial publication in 1847. It was not until the 20th century that scholars began to increasingly recognize and appreciate its literary values. The existent analyses of *Wuthering Heights* vary from romanticism (Nussbaum, 1996), feminism (Stoneman, 1992), and gothic studies (Rena-Dozie, 2010) to postcolonial criticism (Tsao, 2014). Over time, *Wuthering Heights* is considered to be on par with *Pride and Prejudice* in terms of reputation. However, the two novels are rarely put together to compare by scholars. The only

few articles comparing the two novels include What kind of love is in *Pride and Prejudice* and *Wuthering Heights* (Hernández, 2004), *Realism in Pride and Prejudice, Hard times and Wuthering Heights* (Sartori, n.d.), and *Dreading He Knew Not What: Masculinities, Structural Spaces, Law and the Gothic in The Castle of Otranto, Pride and Prejudice, and Wuthering Heights* (Morse, 2013), but few of them compare the two novels from psychological aspects. This essay aims to analyze two heroines, Elizabeth in *Pride and Prejudice* and Catherine in *Wuthering Heights*, with the id, ego and super-ego principle. Sigmund Freud partitioned mental life into three agencies, id, ego and superego. A confluence of the three psychological factors impacts both Catherine and Elizabeth, but their interaction produces disparate outcomes for each character.

“Id” Exists in Catherine and Elizabeth

The id is “the oldest and most primitive psychic agency, representing the biological foundations of personality. It is the reservoir of basic instinctual drives, particularly sexual (libidinal) drives, which motivate the organism to seek pleasure” (Lapsley, 2011). Both Elizabeth and Catherine are driven by such instincts. Little Catherine is “a wild, wicked slip” (Bronte, 2008). “Her spirits were always at high-water mark, her tongue always going singing, laughing, and plaguing everybody who would not do the same” (Bronte, 2008). She and Heathcliff, as rebels of the Manorial life, spend their childhood together in the solitude of the wilderness, far from civilized society and close to nature. In this special environment, Catherine finds her id, the essence of her true self, which is full of the wild, primitive instincts of human nature. She is like a newborn baby, ignorant of values and morality. She finds her id is the same as Heathcliff, “because he (Heathcliff) ’s more myself than I am. Whatever our souls are made of, his and mine are the same” (Bronte, 2008). Actually, her love for Heathcliff implies her pursuit of the id, which is stimulated by her basic instinctual drives.

Like Catherine, Elizabeth also has her id. Deep in her heart, there is a desire for love, which is motivated by sexual drives. When Mr. Darcy shows up at the ball, almost everyone is attracted by him, including Elizabeth. “He was tall, handsome, and noble-looking. Within five minutes of his arrival, almost everyone knew he had an income of ten thousand a year” (Austen, 2011). It was Darcy’s arrogant attitude that lowers his image in Elizabeth’s mind, causing Elizabeth to hide her inner id. In fact, her younger sister Lydia is the embodiment of Elizabeth’s id, who is fond of fantasy, and eager for love. Lydia prioritizes the “pleasure principle” above all else, disregarding her family’s honor, moral codes, and age restrictions in pursuit of her love. “Lydia has eloped with one of his officers—Wickham!” (Austen, 2011). She is driven to satisfy her instincts and pleasure, even if it means going against societal norms. Although Elizabeth treats Lydia’s elopement as a family stain, it is undeniable that she also has a yearning for love inside her, only to be constrained by the superego.

“Super-Ego” Exists in Catherine and Elizabeth

The id can be suppressed by the superego, the moral and ethical part of the psyche, which is concerned with right and wrong and strives to uphold societal and cultural norms and values (Freud, 1967). The id is buried deeply by the two female protagonists because of cultivation. When Catherine accidentally wandered into the neighboring Thrushcross Grange, she is transported to a world of exquisite beauty that contrasted sharply with the wild moors of *Wuthering Heights*. “we saw ah! it was beautiful a splendid place.....” (Bronte, 2008). If *Wuthering Heights* represents primitive nature, then Thrushcross Grange is a symbol of civilized society, where Catherine’s super-ego and moral principles are awakened for the first time. As she peers out of the window, she beholds a world brimming with material comforts and the trappings of a refined society. It is a place where social standing and material possessions hold immense allure for her. Katherine’s five-week

stay at Thrushcross Grange has a transformative effect on her, which drives her to become a lady with a dignified and elegant demeanor. Catherine sees in Linton, the young master of Thrushcross Grange, a model of gentleness and wealth, and begins to regard him as a point of reference to gauge her own behavior and her wild nature. So, when Linton is coming to visit, she even tries to get rid of Heathcliff, the symbol of her own id. "Isabella and Edgar Linton talked of calling this afternoon. . . . As it rains, I hardly expect them; but they may come, and if they do, you run the risk of being scolded for no good" (Bronte, 2008). In this way, Linton embodies the superego in Catherine's psychological makeup, guiding her toward socially acceptable behavior. She even acknowledges this kind of admiration as love: "I love the ground under his feet, and the air over his head, and everything he touches, and every word he says. I love all his looks, and all his actions, and him entirely and altogether" (Bronte, 2008).

For Elizabeth, her instinctual pursuit of blind love is suppressed by the superego. When she hears Darcy's judgment on her: "She is tolerable, but not handsome enough to tempt me" (Austen, 2001), she perceives Darcy's arrogance, so her id is instantly hidden from her and suppressed under superego, as her wounded pride causes her to feel shame, which in turn causes her indifference to Darcy: "Elizabeth remained with no very cordial feelings toward him" (Austen, 2001). Elizabeth's love is restrained by her superego and disguised by her defensive prejudice. Actually, Jane, who is incapable of expressing love for Mr. Bentley, is the embodiment of Elizabeth's superego. "she (Jane) had begun to entertain for him from the first, and was in a way to be very much in love. . . . it was not likely to be discovered by the world in general, since Jane united, with great strength of feeling, a composure of temper and a uniform cheerfulness of manner" (Austen, 2001). She follows the principle of goodness, forcing herself to behave in a way that was perfectly in line with what society required of women at the time, haughtily suppressing her love for Mr. Bentley. However, her repressed and intense love makes it difficult for her to

express her true feelings. This misunderstanding leads to Bentley misinterpreting her intentions and eventually separating her and Bentley. The superego triumphs over the id, but the story remained imperfect. Only when it achieves a state of balance between the id and superego can the story culminate in a truly harmonious resolution.

"Ego" Exists in Catherine and Elizabeth

Except for the id and superego, another agency named "ego" exists in individuals' personalities. The ego is the rational and conscious part of the psyche, which mediates between the id and the superego. It seeks to satisfy the desires of the id in a way that is socially acceptable and in line with the individual's values and goals. As Liang stated: "The "id" chases after pleasure, and the "super-ego" is in pursuit of the "perfect", but the function of the "ego" is to satisfy the desire of the "id" and the requirement of the "super-ego" in accordance with reality principle" (Liang, 2011). When the ego effectively fulfills its role, it can establish a harmonious balance between the id and superego, but if it fails to do so, the two may be locked in perpetual conflict.

Catherine, the symbol of the ego, tries to reconcile the conflict between Heathcliff and Linton, which represents the struggle between ego and superego but results in failure. The encounter with Linton leads Catherine to adopt Thrushcross Grange's indoctrination. In order to conform to societal expectations and maintain her status, Catherine suppresses her primal instincts and desires that are inherent in her id, so she perceives Heathcliff, a rebellious youth, as a degrading prospect for marriage. "It would degrade me to marry Heathcliff now; so he shall never know how I love him. . . . and Linton's is as different as a moonbeam from lightning, or frost from fire" (Bronte, 2008). She strives to constantly repress her id and appeal to her superego, she cannot separate herself from Heathcliff, who is an essential part of her being. When she is going to give up Heathcliff and accept Linton's marriage proposal, a sound in

her heart tells her it is a wrong choice. “HERE! and HERE!.....in whichever place the soul lives. In my soul and in my heart, I’m convinced I’m wrong!” The betrayal of her id causes Heathcliff’s leave and takes away her source of joy, “I cannot say why I felt so wildly wretched” (Bronte, 2008). What’s worse, she finds that since her chance encounters with Linton at the age of twelve, she seems to have been torn into two different pieces and the distance from the wilderness and *Wuthering Heights* made her lose herself: “supposing at twelve years old I had been wrenched from the Heights, and every early association, and my all in all, as Heathcliff was at that time, and been converted at a stroke into Mrs. Linton, the lady of Thrushcross Grange, and the wife of a stranger: an exile, and outcast, thenceforth, from what had been my world. You may fancy a glimpse of the abyss where I grovelled!.....Oh, I’m burning! I wish I were out of doors! I wish I were a girl again, half savage and hardy, and free; and laughing at injuries, not maddening under them! (Bronte, 2008)

The return of Heathcliff triggers a climactic conflict within Catherine’s psyche between her id and superego, leading to a fragmentation of her personality and descent into madness, causing her immense suffering and bringing her to the brink of a complete breakdown.

On the contrary, Elizabeth takes advantage of her ego perfectly to coordinate her primal desires and rational consciousness. Although she longs for perfect love, she keeps her sanity. When Mr. Darcy shows up at the ball, almost everyone, including Elizabeth, is attracted by him. However, Elizabeth is not completely blinded by Darcy’s perfect image, instead, she judges him from the perspective of a bystander: “I know him as well as I ever wish to..... I find him very disagreeable” (Austen, 2001). Although Darcy has caught Elizabeth’s attention, his condescending demeanor and Wickham’s unfavorable depiction of him deepen her initial prejudice against him. Elizabeth’s psyche reaches a point where her superego overpowers her id. However, after Darcy’s confession of love, Elizabeth’s primal desires are reignited, leading her to confront her feelings for Darcy.

Her inner conflicts between her desires and moral conscience intensify, leading to a period of inner turmoil, and finally leads to her re-evaluation of him. As Freud said, “The ego is driven by the id, and is constrained by the super-ego, and is excluded by the reality, for struggling for the economic task that is not completed, so that it can guide all kinds of power and influence to achieve harmony” (Freud, 2001). In the midst of her time with Darcy, Elizabeth gradually abandons her prejudices and finally accepts Darcy’s proposal of marriage.

Conclusion

In conclusion, both Elizabeth and Catherine embody the three psychological states of id, ego, and superego. During Catherine’s childhood, she and Heathcliff, who represented her primal impulses, or id, were inseparable. They were each other’s closest and sole companions, frequently engaging in unbridled play and running wildly across the wilderness. The two of them were so connected that they seemed to become one, with Catherine feeling as though Heathcliff was a part of her. However, when she met Linton at Thrushcross Grange, her superego awakened, and she developed a sense of reason and social morality. Despite her ego’s attempts to reconcile the conflicting forces of her id and superego, it fails. She is thus torn between her ego and superego, and the different sizes of “Catherine Earnshaw”, “Catherine Heathcliff” and “Catherine Linton” (Bronte 8) that she writes on her bedroom windowsill are a manifestation of this ambivalence, leading her death in the end.

In contrast, Elizabeth is adept at utilizing her ego to effectively manage and balance her instinctual impulses and rational awareness. Initially, she harbored an attraction to Darcy despite his haughty demeanor, which deterred her from engaging with him. Subsequent to his proposal, her psyche underwent a profound conflict between her instinctual desires and her moral values. In the end, her ego helped her achieve a state of balance between her id and superego, leading her to reevaluate Darcy and reconcile her internal strife.

References

- Almond, R. (1989). Psychological change in Jane Austen's *Pride and prejudice*. *The Psychoanalytic Study of the Child*, 44(1), 307-324. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00797308.1989.11822655>
- Awan, A.G. & Nasir, A.A. (2018). Matrimonial issues and Marxist approach in “*Pride and Prejudice*” by Jane Austin. *Global Journal of Management, Social Sciences and Humanities*, 4(3), 651-676.
- Brontë, E. (2008). *Wuthering heights*. San Francisco: Ignatius Press.
- Freud, S. (1924). Neurosis and psychosis. In Austen, J. (Ed.). *Pride and prejudice*. Peterborough: Broadview Press.
- Freud, S. (1967). *Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, vol. 3 In P. Edwards (Ed.). New York: Collier Macmillan.
- Hernández, P.S. (2004). What kind of love is at work in *Pride and Prejudice* and *Wuthering Heights*? *Journal of English Studies*, 4, 185-196. <https://doi.org/10.18172/jes.95>
- Lapsley, D.K. & Stey, P.C. (2011). Id, ego, and superego. In V.S. Ramachandran (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Human Behavior (2nd Ed.)*. Amsterdam: Elsevier.
- Liang, Y. (2011). The Id, Ego and Super-Ego in *Pride and Prejudice*. *International Education Studies*, 4(2), 177-181. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v4n2p177>
- Morse, S.E. (2013). *Dreading He Knew Not What: Masculinities, Structural Spaces, Law and the Gothic in The Castle of Otranto, Pride and Prejudice, and Wuthering Heights*. Pitzer Senior Theses. Paper 58. Retrieved from: http://scholarship.claremont.edu/pitzer_theses/58
- Nussbaum, M.C. (1996). *Wuthering Heights: The Romantic Ascent*. *Philosophy and Literature*, 20(2), 362-382. <https://doi.org/10.1353/phl.1996.0076>
- Rena-Dozier, E. (2010). Gothic criticisms: wuthering heights and nineteenth-century literary history. *Elb*, 77(3), 757-775. <https://doi.org/10.1353/elh.2010.0000>
- Sartori, L. (2010). Realism in *Pride and Prejudice*, *Hard Times* and *Wuthering Heights*. *Education*, 5, 45-59.
- Stoneman, P. (1992). Feminist criticism of *Wuthering Heights*. *Critical Survey*, 4(2), 147-153.
- Sultana, K.Z.S. (2012). Feminism in Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice*. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 1(2), 523-536. <https://doi.org/10.36347/sjahss.2017.v05i08.001>
- Tsao, T. (2014). Postcolonial life and death: a process-based comparison of emily bronte's wuthering Heights and ayu utami's saman. *Comparative Literature*, 66(1), 95-112. <https://doi.org/10.1215/00104124-2414950>